

200 100 0 200 km

- ▲ archaeological site
- border
- river
- capital
- Khazar Khaganate
- COUNTRY

DEM: Natural Earth v2.3.2
 Admin: The World Bank
 Hydro: Natural Earth, OSM, RIMES

Projection: WGS 1984
 Datum: WGS 1984

